

Analysis of public perceptions towards agrotourism (Case Study of The Zafarm Agrotourism in Palembang City)

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the public's perception of The Zafarm Agrotourism. The sample of respondents in this study used an accidental sampling technique, which was calculated using the Slovin formula so that the number of respondents was 72 people. The analytical method used is qualitative descriptive analysis. Data was collected using questionnaires both directly and online via Google Drive links and barcodes. The results of this research show that the public's perception of The Zafarm Agrotourism in terms of the dimensions of attractions, accessibility and amenities is in agreement, where the public's perception of The Zafarm Agrotourism object in terms of the attractions dimension has a total score of 1.501, which is in the score range of 1.224–1.511 according to the criteria agree, the public's perception of The Zafarm Agrotourism object in terms of the accessibility dimension has a total score of 579, which is in the score range 489–603 with the criteria of agree, the public's perception of The Zafarm Agrotourism object, which is viewed from the amenity dimension, has a total score of 578, which is in the score range of 489 –603 with agree criteria. This means that The Zafarm Agrotourism object is well received by the community. The natural beauty, unique experiences in learning about agricultural cultivation with the cultural nuances of Palembang City, the availability of infrastructure, affordable road access, and other supporting facilities such as learning media for the visiting public are the attractions of The Zafarm Agrotourism.

Keywords: Perception; Agrotourism; The Zafarm; Tourist Attraction; Public

1. Introduction

Urban agriculture is an agricultural activity in a broad sense that involves the utilization or reuse of existing natural resources to obtain production and processing of production results from various types of food and non-food crops, fisheries and livestock carried out in urban areas. Urban agriculture has a role as part of the food supply chain in urban household food security, utilizing limited land and urban waste into added economic value, and opens up business opportunities and can improve the welfare of urban communities [1]. The presence of agriculture in urban areas and areas around urban areas provides positive value not only in meeting food needs but also has practical values that can have an impact on the ecological and economic sustainability of urban areas.

Agrotourism is an integrated and coordinated system of activities for the development of agricultural tourism in relation to environmental conservation. Agrotourism is the development of an agricultural pattern that combines agriculture and tourism by utilizing agricultural cultivation activities from the start of cultivation to obtaining agricultural products of various commodities and business scales with the aim of providing recreational experiences in agriculture [2]. The agrotourism trend can now be found in Palembang City. Nowadays, agricultural land in urban areas has been used as a tourist spot, the land has been modified in such a way that it is comfortable and attractive and can be accepted by the

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community as a tourist area object. Further development of agrotourism in Palembang City currently is by providing education to visitors or better known as agroedutourism. The aim of Agroedutourism is to provide knowledge, experience and broader understanding related to agricultural activities in a broad sense which includes farming, animal husbandry, fisheries and forestry to local communities and tourists.

One of the agrotourism in Palembang City is The Zafarm. The Zafarm was founded by the parent company, namely PT. ZafaMuliaMandiri. PT. ZafaMuliaMandiri is a company that operates in the field of Umrah travel and tourism services in the city of Palembang and then innovated to build an urban farming model with an agro-tourism concept under the name The Zafarm. In this agro-tourism there is a *green house* on the land where vegetables and fruit are cultivated using a hydroponic system which makes it an attraction for visitors. Apart from that, there is an area for resting and eating for visitors to taste the fruit and processed products being sold. The Zafarm management provides information about hydroponics to visitors so as to increase knowledge and prevent tourists from getting bored from visiting again. Apart from that, the management opens opportunities for students who are interested in doing internships and research so as to broaden the knowledge of the management and students. However, there is something the author wants to study regarding whether The Zafarm Agrotourism is feasible from a technical, economic, social and environmental perspective as a model for urban agricultural development.

Tourist attraction objects consist of natural tourist attractions, cultural tourist attractions and artificial tourist attractions [3]. Success in attracting tourists depends on three important components offered by tourist attractions to tourists, namely attractions, amenities and accessibility [4]. Attractions are anything that is interesting about a tourist attraction so that tourists are interested in visiting that tourist attraction. Tourists visit tourist areas to obtain things they cannot find in their daily lives. A tourist spot will be called a tourist attraction if it has a variety of attractions that are able to attract tourists to visit the tourist destination area [5].

Amenities/facilities are important services that are used to meet the needs of tourists at tourist attractions so as to make tourists feel comfortable in the tourist destination area. The condition of a facility needs to be paid attention to by tourism industry managers, visitors will feel happy if the facility is well maintained [6]. Accessibility is the convenience for tourists in reaching the tourist destination they want to visit. At a tourist attraction, it is very important to provide easy road access, so that tourists can reach the tourist attraction. The existence of accessibility at a tourist attraction can make it easier for tourists to reach an object [7]. In traditional tourist destinations, elements support each other and are interrelated so that a charming tourist attraction is formed for tourists [8]. Tourists' decisions in visiting tourist attractions are based on the tourism components/products offered [9].

A tourist attraction can develop and be used as a tourist destination by tourists depending on the perception or assessment tourists give to the tourist attraction. Perception is an opinion or impression about the experience expressed by an individual regarding an object that is a stimulus that is captured using the five senses. The experiences they have experienced can be used as a reference in perceiving something. The public's perception of agrotourism in urban areas, especially Palembang City, gives rise to a positive perception because it provides a choice of new tourist attractions in urban areas which can become holiday destinations to relieve people's fatigue. Perception is the process of giving meaning, interpreting stimuli and sensations received by an individual, and is greatly influenced by internal and external factors for each individual [10]. The perception of every human being certainly has a different point of view in thinking which perceives something in the form of positive perception or negative perception so that it influences visible or real human actions.

2. Materials and Methods

The method used in this research is a qualitative method with a case study approach. This research intends to provide a description of the development of agrotourism businesses in Palembang City. Data collection techniques use interview techniques and questionnaires both directly and via *Goggle Drive links*. In this research, the sampling technique used was *accidental sampling*. *Accidental sampling* is taking respondents as samples based on chance, that is, anyone who meets the researcher by chance can be used as a sample, if the person they meet by chance is suitable as a data source according to the main criteria [11].

The respondents taken were visitors who came to The Zafarm Agro-edutourism at the time the research took place. The total population of visitors in a month is 200 people, so the sample taken is calculated using slovin as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{200}{1 + 200(0,15^2)}$$

N = 72

Based on Slovin's calculations, the number of samples taken was 72 respondents.

The type of data in this research is qualitative data with the data source being primary data. The data collection method is a questionnaire using a Likert scale. The Likert scale is used to measure attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena [12] . There are five answers to each statement with a score of 5 to 1 in the categories of strongly agree to strongly disagree. Questionnaires were used to collect data regarding tourists' perceptions of the TengananPegringsingan tourist attraction.

The analysis technique in this research is descriptive data analysis. Descriptive analysis using a Likert scale which is a tool for measuring attitudes from a very positive to a very negative level, to show the extent of agreement or disagreement with the statement proposed by the researcher [13] . The attitude scores can be seen in table 1.

Table 1 Likert Scale on Community Perceptions of Agrotourism

No.	Community Attitude Scale		
	Attitude	Score	Category (%)
1	Strongly agree	5	81-100
2	Agree	4	61-80
3	Neutral	3	41-60
4	Don't agree	2	21-40
5	Strongly Disagree	1	1-20

Determining the highest score and lowest score from all alternative answers. Number of highest scores = highest score x number of statements x number of respondents. Number of lowest scores = lowest score x number of questions x number of respondents. Determining the interval range uses the following formula:

Calculation of descriptive analysis for each dimension; Class interval = Range : C

Table 2 Descriptive Analysis Calculations

Perception	Highest Score	Lowest Score	Score Range	Class Intervals
Attractions	1800	360	1440	288
Accessibility	720	144	576	115
Amenities	720	144	576	115

Based on the calculations in table 2, the criteria for tourists' perceptions of the agrotourism object The Zafarm Palembang City can be obtained which can be seen in table 3.

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the categories of perception of attractions are divided into 5 with a score range of 360 – 647 including the strongly disagree category, a score range of 648 – 935 including the disagree category, a score range of 936 – 1,223 including the neutral category, a score range of 1,224 – 1,511 including the agree category and a score range of 1.512 – 1.800 including the strongly agree category.

Table 3 Criteria and Score Ranges for Perception of Tourist Attractions

Score Range	Category
1.512 – 1.8 00	Strongly agree
1,224 – 1.511	Agree
936 – 1.223	Neutral
648 – 935	Don't agree
36 0 – 647	Strongly Disagree

Table 4 Criteria and Score Ranges for Perceived Tourism Accessibility

Score Range	Category
604 – 720	Strongly agree
489 – 603	Agree
374 – 488	Neutral
2 5 9 – 373	Don't agree
144 – 258	Strongly Disagree

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the categories of perceived accessibility are divided into 5 with a score range of 144 – 258 including the strongly disagree category, a score range of 2 5 9 – 373 including the disagree category, a score range of 374 – 488 including the neutral category, a score range of 489 – 603 is in the agree category and the score range 604 – 720 is in the strongly agree category.

Table 5 Criteria and Score Ranges for Perceptions of Tourist Amenities

Score Range	Category
604 – 720	Strongly agree
489 – 603	Agree
374 – 488	Neutral
2 5 9 – 373	Don't agree
144 – 258	Strongly Disagree

Table 6 Criteria and Composite Score Ranges for Perceptions of Attractions, Accessibility and Tourist Amenities

Score Range	Category
2.721 – 3.240	Strongly agree
2.203 – 2.720	Agree
1.684 – 2.202	Neutral
1.166 – 1.683	Don't agree
648 – 1.165	Strongly Disagree

Based on Table 5, it can be seen that the categories of perceived accessibility are divided into 5 with a score range of 144 – 258 including the strongly disagree category, a score range of 259 – 373 including the disagree category, a score range of 374 – 488 including the neutral category, a score range of 489 – 603 is in the agree category and the score range 604 – 720 is in the strongly agree category.

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that the categories in the combined perception of attractions, accessibility and amenities are divided into 5 with a score range of 648–1,165 including the strongly disagree category, a score range of 1,166–1,683 including the disagree category, a score range of 1,684–2,202 including the neutral category, a range of a score of 2,203–2,720 is in the agree category and a score range of 2,721–3,240 is in the strongly agree category.

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the data analysis calculations carried out, the public's perception of The Zafaram tourist attraction in terms of the dimensions of attractions, accessibility and amenities can be seen in the following table:

Table 7 Results of research on public perceptions of the Zafaram Agrotourism in terms of attraction dimensions

Dimensions	Indicator	Score	Score Range	Category
Attractions	Natural beauty and unique experiences	298	244-299	Agree
	The nuances of local traditions and culture	294	244-299	Agree
	The people of Palembang are interested in visiting	301	300-358	VeryAgree
	Good level of security	293	244-299	Agree
	Harvest yourself from melon plants and catfish	315	300-358	Strongly agree
Amount		1.501	1.224 – 1.511	Agree

Based on Table 7, it shows that the public's perception of the Zafaram Agrotourism, which is viewed from the attraction dimension on the indicator of unique and beautiful natural beauty, has a score of 298, which is in the score range of 244-299 with the criteria of agreeing. On the indicator of nuances of local traditions and culture, it has a score of 294, which is in the score range 244-299 with the agree criteria. The indicator that Palembang people are interested in visiting has a score of 301, which is in the score range of 300-358 with the criteria of strongly agree. The indicator for a good level of security has a score of 293, which is in the score range 244-299 with the agree criteria. For the self-harvest indicator, melons and catfish have a score of 315, which is in the score range of 300-358 with the criteria of strongly agree. Overall, the public/visitors' perception of the Zafaram Agrotourism in terms of the attraction dimension has a total score of 1,501, which is in the score range of 1,224 – 1,511 with the criteria of agreeing.

Table 8 Results of research on public perceptions of the Zafaram Agrotourism in terms of the accessibility dimension

Dimensions	Indicator	Score	Score Range	Category
Accessibility	Complete infrastructure condition	302	246-303	Agree
	Road signs	277	246-303	Agree
Amount		579	489 – 603	Agree

Based on Table 8, it shows that the public's perception of the Zafaram Agrotourism, which is viewed from the accessibility dimension of the infrastructure availability indicator, has a score of 302, which is in the score range of 246-303 with the agree criteria. The indicator for the availability of road signs has a score of 277, which is in the score range 246-303 with the agree criteria. So the public's perception of The Zafaram Agrotourism in the accessibility dimension has a total score of 579, which is in the score range of 489 – 603 with the agree criteria.

Table 9 Results of research on public perceptions of the Zafarm Agrotourism in terms of the amenities dimension

Dimensions	Indicator	Score	Score Range	Category
Amenities	Availability of accommodation facilities in agrotourism	291	246-303	Agree
	Availability of supporting facilities for agrotourism	287	246-303	Agree
Amount		578	489 – 603	Agree

Based on Table 9, it shows that the public's perception of the Zafarm Agrotourism, which is reviewed from the amenities dimension in the indicator of the availability of accommodation facilities in agrotourism, has a score of 291, which is in the score range of 246-303 with the criteria of agreeing. The indicator for the availability of supporting facilities in agrotourism has a score of 287, which is in the score range 246-303 with the agree criteria. Overall, the public/visitors' perception of the Zafarm Agrotourism in terms of the amenities dimension has a total score of 578, which is in the score range of 489 – 603 with the criteria of agreeing.

Table 10 Results of research on public perceptions of the Zafarm Agrotourism in terms of the dimensions of attractions, accessibility and amenities

Dimensions	Score	Score Range	Category
Attractions	1.501	1.224 – 1.511	Positive
Accessibility	579	489 – 603	Positive
Amenities	578	489 – 603	Positive
Amount	2.658	2.203 – 2.720	Positive

Based on Table 4.8. The results of research on public perceptions of the Zafarm Agrotourism, in terms of the dimensions of attractions, accessibility and amenities, obtained a total score of 2.658, including a score range of 2.203 – 2.720. This interprets that the public has a positive perception of agrotourism and the Zafarm Agrotourism provides important components of agrotourism, namely attractions, accessibility and amenities.

This is in line with the following research that everything that is interesting about a tourist attraction is a factor behind people's decisions to visit a tourist attraction. The availability of various agrotourism attractions can be an important motivation in encouraging visitor attendance [14].

The results of this research are also in line with research that reaching a tourist attraction is the end of a journey so it is necessary to fulfill the accessibility aspect, which means that a tourist attraction must be easy to reach and easy for the public to find [7]. Apart from that, if a tourist attraction provides tourist facilities that visitors need, it will encourage people to visit and enjoy a tourist attraction for a relatively long time [7]. Availability of food and drink stalls and entrance tickets for tourists to enjoy the tourist attractions visited. The availability of supporting facilities for tourist attractions can also be equipped starting from having a prayer room, having clean toilets, having a parking space for tourist vehicles, having a rest area for visitors, having a rubbish bin and the availability of information about The Zafarm tourist attraction on the internet and social media. The supporting facilities available at The Zafarm tourist attraction can be said to be quite complete. Complete and high-quality amenities can make visitors feel comfortable, thereby creating a sense of enjoyment during a visit to a tourist destination.

4. Conclusion

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that tourists' perceptions of The Zafarm Agrotourism object in terms of the dimensions of attractions, accessibility and amenities have a total score of 2,658, which is in the score range of 2,203 – 2,720 with the criteria of agreeing. This shows that The Zafarm Agrotourism offers natural beauty and a unique experience in learning about agricultural cultivation to tourists with the safe and comfortable cultural nuances of Palembang City which can make tourists interested in visiting. This is supported by the availability of complete infrastructure such as tourist road signs at The Zafarm Agrotourism. Apart from that, the availability of accommodation facilities and supporting facilities such as learning media for visiting tourists adds to the attraction of The Zafarm Agrotourism.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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